

COMPOUND FORMATION IN SOLUTIONS. PART I. PYRIDINE AND ACETIC ACID.

BY S. VENKATARAMAN.

Singularities in physical properties accompanying compound formation in binary liquid mixtures are discussed, and it is pointed out that a maximum in viscosity-concentration curve is not a conclusive evidence of compound formation. Intensity and depolarisation of scattered light and magnetic susceptibilities of pyridine-acetic acid mixtures of different concentrations are determined and these experiments seem to indicate the formation of a chemical complex containing 60 mol. % of the acid and 40 mol. % of pyridine. Viscosity-concentration curve, however, shows a maximum for a mixture containing 78 mol. % of the acid.

Two liquids having considerable affinity for each other combine to form a chemical complex when mixed. All cases of compound formation in solutions are accompanied by certain singularities in physical properties of the mixture, those that were mostly studied being, heat of solutions, density, viscosity, surface tension, vapour pressure and refractive index. Particularly viscosities of solutions were widely studied to consider compound formation (Hatschek, "Viscosity of Liquids", 1928 Chapter IX).

The early work on the viscosity of binary mixtures was to find out the law of "ideal" mixtures which has, however, proved elusive so far. The large amount of experimental data accumulated show that most mixtures exhibit viscosity maxima for a particular concentration of the components. Dunstan and his collaborators (Dunstan and Thole, "Viscosity of Liquids", 1917, p. 44) have pointed out that components of mixtures showing maxima in their viscosity-concentration curves are generally those which have a considerable affinity for each other and therefrom conclude that a maximum in viscosity-concentration curve should be regarded as indicating compound formation between the components in the mixture. The prodigious amount of experimental results supplied by Dunstan and co-worker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 817; 1907, **91**, 1728; 1913, **103**, 1108), Tsakalatos (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1908, *iv*, **3**, 134) and others seem to point out that the above view is fairly conclusive. This view is supported by actual demonstration of compound formation; we know from chemical evidence, that a hydrate is formed when acetic acid and water are mixed in the ratio of about 80% by weight of the acid to about 20% by weight of water. Viscosity-concentration curve also shows a maximum in mixture containing 80% by weight of the acid,

In liquid mixtures, besides the large change in viscosity that indicates formation of chemical complexes, there are other singularities in physical properties, which also seem to indicate the same chemical combination. In acetone-chloroform mixture a minimum in the vapour pressure curve (Zawidzki, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, **39**, 129) occurs for about the same proportion of the components giving a viscosity maximum (Faust, *ibid.*, 1912, **79**, 97); a maximum deviation from the mixture law values of magnetic susceptibilities (Buchner, *Nature*, 1931, **128**, 301; Ranganadham, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, **6**, 421) is also exhibited for the same proportion of the components. Density determination of acetic acid-water mixture (Oudemans, L. B. M. Tables) indicates a maximum density at 80% by weight of the acid. Krishnamurti's work (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, **6**, 401) on Raman-effect in acetic acid solutions shows the appearance of a new line (1707 cm.^{-1}) and the disappearance of the line (1667 cm.^{-1}) originally present, when the concentration reaches 77% of the acid. The magnetic susceptibilities of acetic acid-water mixtures determined by Sibaiya and Venkataramaiah (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, **7**, 393) also show a maximum deviation from the mixture law relations for the same proportion of the components.

A comparison of the viscosity and vapour pressure data available shows that for a maximum in the viscosity curve of a certain mixture, there corresponds a minimum in the vapour pressure curve and *vice versa* (cf. Faust, *loc. cit.*; Yajnik, Bhalla, Talwar and Soofi, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, **118**, 305). Mixtures of pyridine and aniline with acetic acid show maxima in viscosity curves and minima in vapour pressure curves; and the mixture of acetone and carbon disulphide shows a viscosity minimum and vapour pressure maximum. Zawidzki (*loc. cit.*) has shown that pyridine-water mixture behaves anomalously, as both viscosity and vapour pressure curves show maxima. This is explained by supposing that the compound formed in solution is dissociated to the extent of 96% in the vapour. Krishnamurti's work (*loc. cit.*) shows that a compound is formed when the liquids are mixed in the proportion necessary to produce viscosity maximum.

The vapour pressure data by Zawidzki for acetic acid-pyridine mixtures show an anomalous behaviour, as the vapour pressure curve indicates a minimum for a mixture containing 50 mol. % of the acid and two points of inflexion corresponding to mixtures containing 30 and 80 mol. % of the acid. He suggests the possibility of the existence of two compounds, one containing more pyridine corresponding to the first point of inflexion and the other containing more acid corresponding to the second point of inflexion. Viscosity curve shows only one maximum at 78 mol. % of the acid, while

the density of the mixture is a maximum at 86 mol. % of the acid. But according to Hatschek ("Viscosity of Liquids," 1928, p. 248) there is considerable evidence to show the formation of a compound containing three molecules of acetic acid and two of pyridine, *i.e.*, in a mixture containing 60 mol. % of the acid. Hence this work was undertaken to see if other physical properties of the mixture show any singularities indicating compound formation.

Among the physical properties which have not been widely used so far, are the intensity and depolarisation of light scattered by solutions. Ostwald (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, 9, 43) showed a parallelism between the viscosity and opalescence of partially miscible liquids as critical solution temperature is approached. Ray (*Proc. Indian Assoc. Cult. Sci.*, 1924, 9, 19) has shown that the intensity of light scattered exhibits a maximum for a particular concentration, while the depolarising factor shows a minimum for another concentration. To verify his formula for scattering in binary mixtures, selection of liquids was arbitrary and the mixtures were not those that were likely to form chemical complexes. Hence the study of the variation of depolarising factor and the intensity of the scattered light in acetic acid-pyridine mixtures, in which a compound is supposed to exist, has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Light Scattering in Acetic Acid-pyridine Mixtures.

Measurement of Depolarisation.—The liquids employed were rendered dust-free by the method originally used by Martin and others (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1920, 24, 478; *cf.* also Raman and Seshagiri Rao, *Phil. Mag.*, 1923, 45, 625). Several bulbs containing dust-free pure liquids and solutions of known concentrations, including those with 60, 78 and 86 mol. % of the acid were prepared. (A large amount of heat is given off on mixing the pure liquids presumably indicating compound formation).

Sunlight was reflected by means of a heliostat on the object glass of a telescope (aperture 4", focal length, 1 meter), placed in a dark room. The bulbs were immersed one after another into a rectangular tank (the outside of which was blackened leaving only three windows as in the case of the bulbs) containing distilled water. The narrow intense beam of sunlight emerging out of the tube of the telescope was made to pass axially through the bulb immersed in the tank.

The depolarising factor, γ , of the scattered light was measured by means of a double image prism and nicol in the usual manner (Wood, "Physical

Optics," 3rd Ed., p. 432). The results obtained (curve I, Fig. 1), indicate a minimum in the depolarisation-concentration curve, which occurs in a mixture containing 60 mol. % of the acid.

FIG. 1.

Intensity Measurements.—The same bulbs were used for the measurement of the intensity of scattered light. The bulb containing pyridine was used as the standard. The other bulbs were placed one after another, in contact with and by the side of the pyridine bulb, so that the light passed straight through the bulbs. A rotating sector photometer (Hilger's) was used for the measurement of intensity. The intensity-concentration curve (curve II, Figure 1), shows a maximum for the mixture showing a minimum in the γ -concentration curve.

Measurement of Magnetic Susceptibility.—Quincke's method was used for the determination of the magnetic susceptibilities of the mixtures. Two uniform capillary tubes, of not too narrow a bore, were supported vertically between the flat pole pieces of a large Pye's electromagnet specified to carry a maximum current of 12 amps. Each capillary tube was connected at both ends to a wider tube, about a foot away, by glass tubing so as to form a closed system. One of the capillary tubes contained pure distilled water, whose susceptibility was assumed to be -0.720×10^{-6} . The other tube was for liquids to be experimented upon.

If δ is the depression of the meniscus in any one of the tubes on switching on the current, then the specific susceptibility χ of the liquid in it is given by the relation,

$$\chi = \frac{2\delta g}{H^2} + \frac{\rho_0}{\rho} \chi_0$$

where H is the magnetic field, ρ , the density of the liquid, ρ_0 and χ_0 , are the density and susceptibility respectively of the air-vapour mixture above the meniscus. The above relation reduces to

$$\chi = \frac{2\delta g}{H^2}$$

as the second term on the right is negligibly small compared to the first. If χ_1, δ_1 are the susceptibility and depression in the meniscus in the case of water in one of the tubes, and χ_2 and δ_2 stand for the same quantities in the case of the liquid in the other tube, we have

$$\frac{\chi_1}{\chi_2} = \frac{\delta_1}{\delta_2}$$

whence χ_2 can be calculated assuming χ_1 .

To make sure that the results obtained by this method are reliable, certain liquids, *viz.*, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, acetic acid, and pyridine, whose susceptibilities are definitely known, were first used for investigation and the results obtained agree quite closely with the standard values in the International Critical Tables.

The bulbs used in the previous experiments were opened and the susceptibilities of the mixtures contained in them were determined. In Table II the experimental results are recorded in the third column and the second column gives the values for the corresponding mixtures calculated from the additive law. The last column gives the percentage deviation from the mixture law values. The maximum deviation occurs in a mixture containing 60 mol. % of the acid.

TABLE I.

Mixture (Mol % acid).	Susceptibility		% Deviation.
	Calc.	Found.	
0	...	-0.637×10^{-6}	...
10	-0.627×10^{-6}	-0.625	0.319
30	-0.603	-0.611	1.33
50	-0.578	-0.590	2.08
60	-0.569	-0.588	3.34
78	-0.553	-0.562	1.63
86	-0.527	-0.535	1.52
100	...	-0.503	...

DISCUSSION.

The depolarisation and intensity measurements of scattered light and magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate the existence of a chemical complex containing three molecules of the acid and two of pyridine. But the data for viscosity, density and vapour pressure do not confirm this conclusion. The viscosity maximum is obtained with a mixture containing 78 mol.% of the acid and density maximum with a mixture containing 86 mol.% of the acid. The suggestion put forward by Zawidzki and referred to earlier in this paper could not be verified, as physical properties other than vapour pressure, do not seem to show any singularities at points corresponding to the two points of inflexion in his vapour pressure curve.

It is interesting to note that viscosity maximum in this case does not definitely indicate compound formation. It is therefore to be doubted whether any maximum in a viscosity-concentration curve may be safely assumed to be due to the formation of a compound, although the converse that maximum occurs whenever there is chemical combination is generally held to be true. An objection similar to this was raised by Senter ("Outlines of Physical Chemistry", 1925, p. 342), in connection with alcohol-water mixtures. Kurnakow and his collaborators (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 23, 481), who do not consider the maxima which shift with temperature being sufficient evidence of compound formation, find a new type of graph characteristic of binary mixtures containing compounds. The graph consists of two branches convex to the concentration axis which meet at an angle at the maximum point. The composition corresponding to the maximum point is independent of temperature. Dunstan and Thole (*loc. cit.*) explain the shift of maxima with temperature thus: "The maximum will coincide with the composition of the compound formed only if the viscosity of the compound is greater than one or both the components and if all or a large portion of the components combine". Perhaps the lability of the compound formed might also account for the shift of maximum with temperature.

Hence, in the case of acetic acid-pyridine mixtures, it is possible that the greatest amount of the compound is formed in the mixture containing 60 mol.% of the acid, but the viscosity of the compound being less than one or both the components, it is not a maximum for this particular concentration. The further the addition of acetic acid, the more viscous the component, has the effect of increasing the viscosity till a maximum is reached at 78 mol.% of the acid.

The magnetic susceptibility data show deviations from mixture law values, being about 3.34% for a mixture containing 60 mol. % of the acid. This deviation is quite in accordance with theoretical expectation as the molecules of both pyridine and acetic acid are polar, associated and asymmetric.

The investigation will be extended to the study of Raman-effect and other physical properties of the mixture.

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PHYSICAL LABORATORY,
NIZAM COLLEGE, HYDERABAD, DECCAN.

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